

(REVIEW ARTICLE)

Growth of population in Patiala PUNJAB (2011-2021)

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Abstract

In this study, Growth of population has been analyzed during a specific period of time. The understanding of population growth in an area holds the key to understanding of the demographic structure of the area. Here growth of population has been analyzed in Patiala district over ten years. Patiala district lies in the south eastern part of Punjab. Punjab is the 16th most populous state of India. The change has been expressed in absolute numbers. During last 10 years, there is continuously increase in population. Increasing population presents challenge for provide adequate healthcare, education and employment opportunities for the growing population. If the population increasing every year there should be planning for man power utilization. There should be effort to reduce birth rate through a comprehensive programmed of family planning so that sufficient resources are released for the economic development.

Keywords: Growth; Population; Development; Resources; Planning

1. Introduction

The world's population was estimated to be around 8 million at the advent of agriculture around 8000 BC consequently improvement in food supply permitted the births to exceed the deaths by a modest margin. The population continued to grow very slowly for a pretty long period. Due to the population increase partly due to the man's increasing control over nature and partly due to industrial revolution which enhanced the supporting capacity of the areas. The acceleration in population growth was the product of a decline in mortality and the widening gap between the birth rate and death rate. India stands number one in world's population. The population of India has increased more than four folds since the beginning of 20th century. In the mid-20th century, the country experienced high birth rate and death rate results in rapid population growth. The years 1901-1921 have often been recognized as the period of stagnant population. During this period India's population increased from 236 million to only 248million. This was a period when the mortality rate was very high and often out matched the fertility rate. During 1921 to 1951 the population of India increased from 248 million to 360 million. India during 1921-51 was the result of a sharp decline in the mortality rate of the country. The population during 1951-61 decade increased from 361 million to 439 million. During 1961-71-decade population increased from 439 million to 548 million. During 1971-81 India's population grew from 548 million to 683 million. The decade 1981-91 recorded a growth of 23.79 as against 24.99 during previous decade. For the first time during post-independence period there was a fall in growth rate of the country's population to the 1.20percent. It signals the beginning of new era in the country's demographic history. The growth rate of population during 1991-2001 declined further. The decade recorded a growth rate of 21.54%. Between 2011 and 2021 its population continued to grow at a slightly slower pace compared to previous decades. Punjab is the 16th most populous state of India. The Punjab is a border state and shares 553 km of international border. It shares border with J & K in the north, Himachal Pradesh in the east and Haryana, Rajasthan in the south. It covers an area of 50,362 sq.km. It accounts for 1.5% of total area of the country. There is fourfold increase in the population of Punjab during 1901-201, From 7,544,790 in 1901 to 27,704,236 in 2011.

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1.1. The study area

Patiala district is one of the famous princely districts of Punjab. Forming the south-eastern part of the state, it lies between 20°49' and 30°47' north latitude, 75°58' and 76°54' east longitude.

It is surrounded by the districts of Rathgar Sahib, Rupnagar and the Union Territory of Chandigarh in the north, Sangrur district in the west, Ambala and Kurukshetra districts of neighboring state of Haryana in the east and Kaithal district of Haryana in the south. It has 3,325 sq km area. Patiala is the 4th most populous district of Punjab.

Figure 1 Location of patiala

2. Methodology

The understanding of population growth in an area holds the key to the understanding of the entire demographic structure of the area. Growth of population refers to the change in the numbers during a specific period of time. Here the change going to be expressed in absolute numbers. Patiala 's population in 2001 was 15, 84,780. As per the census 2011, population is 18, 92,282. As per 2021 projected population is 22, 59,628.

Table 1 Population of Patiala

Population of Patiala			
year	population	Decadal	Growth
2001	15,84,780	-	
2011	18,92,282	19.40	
2021	22,59,628	20.47	

SOURCE: CENSUS OF INDIA 2011

Figure 2 Population of Patiala

As given above the last 20 years, population of Patiala has been increasingly continuously. The decadal growth has found for the years. Population growth rate describes the per capita rate of growth of a population. Over last 20 years several factors have influenced population growth in Patiala.

Figure 3 Growth of population in Patiala

Population growth rate is estimated using census data over time. The analysis uses scatterplot graphs to show the growth during last 10 years. This period normally synchronizes with inter censal period. As shown in the map population is rising. Patiala’s population has undergone changes over years. This transition has been influenced by various factors such as improvements in healthcare, education and due to birth exceeding deaths. Since 2011 to 2021 its population continued to increase. But it presents challenge for providing adequate healthcare, education and employment opportunities for the growing population.

2.1. Factor affecting the population growth

The basic determinant of fertility includes fecundity age at marriage, marriage system etc. Different racial groups have been found to exhibit varying birth rates. Demographic factor that control fertility age composition, sex composition, degree of urbanization, duration of marriage and working, non-working status of females are prominent. The social cultural determinant religious background, ethnic structure, educational level, age at marriage, attitude towards family size restrictions and govt. policies are prominent. Factor effecting fertility rate can be either economic or social such as education level and religion, race, level of education, child labor and immigration.

2.2. Challenges

The increasing population puts pressure on the natural resources including water, food and energy. Increased population means more consumption of nonrenewable resources. Sustainable resource management becomes crucial to meet the demands of a growing population while preserving the environment. It becomes essential to manage these resources sustainably to meet the growing demands. Generating enough employment opportunities for the expanding working age population is a significant challenge. A large population poses significant challenges in providing accessible and quality healthcare services to all.

3. Conclusion

It is concluded that population of last ten years has been increasing. The growth of population demands larger for resources. The increasing population aggravates the poverty, worsens the unemployment situation reduces per capita income and increase proportion of unproductive people. On the other hand, population is a progress for the countries having good resources and sound policies. There should be effort to reduce birth rate through a comprehensive programme of family planning so that sufficient resources are released for the economic development. If the population increasing every year there should be planning for man power utilization. Manpower is basically the function of size of population and age composition of population apart from the fertility.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

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